

PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT OF INCORRECT APPROACHES TO EDUCATION ON CHILDREN'S PSYCHOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15699385>

Annotation

The role of education in human life is incomparable, and especially the education given in childhood has a strong impact on the formation of the human personality and mental state. Unfortunately, in many cases, parents or educators make various mistakes or incorrect approaches during the education process. This article analyzes the psychological aspects of incorrect approaches to education that negatively affect the psyche of children, including excessive punishment, neglect, lack of affection and energy, comparing the child, and indifference to his opinion. Especially in preschool and primary school, the child's personality is very sensitive, and any adverse treatment affects his self-esteem, communication with the outside world, and the level of expression of his opinion. The study provides evidence on this problem based on observations and interviews conducted among preschool and primary school students in Andijan region. Psychological prevention, improving the culture of family upbringing and developing pedagogical skills can be an important tool in preventing such negative situations.

Keywords: childhood mentality, upbringing mistakes, psychological trauma, childhood, wrong approach, punishment, parental behavior, lack of affection, mental health in childhood.

Introduction

Childhood is the most important and at the same time the most delicate stage of human life. At this stage, the child is formed not only physically, but also mentally and socially. Who the child feels like, how he perceives the world, how he treats others - all this directly depends on the upbringing he received in early childhood. Every word, action, attitude given in the process of upbringing leaves a psychological mark on the child. Modern psychological research shows that many psychological problems, including self-doubt, anxiety, aggression, self-blame or excessive obedience, arise precisely as a result of improper upbringing. For example, constantly criticizing the child, comparing him with others, ignoring his feelings, and educating him through punishment lead to a low self-esteem in the child. Parents often prioritize control over love. This causes the child to develop fear, lying, and internal dissatisfaction. In some cases, the child suppresses his emotions, which becomes the root of psychosomatic diseases and mental anguish. This article examines the psychological aspects of educational approaches that have a negative impact on the psyche of children. A practical approach is used to the topic based on observations and interviews conducted on the example of the Andijan region. The goal is to analyze how important mistakes made in education harm the psyche of children and to identify measures to prevent them.

Literature analysis

The connection between children's psyche and upbringing has been widely studied in psychology. In the works of Erkin G'oziyev (2019), the positive impact of an atmosphere of love and trust on the child's personality during the upbringing process is emphasized. In his opinion, a negative approach to a child, especially verbal reprimands and constant comparisons, leads to the child feeling "unworthy".

The theories of international psychologists - J. Bowlby and E. Erikson - deeply analyze the role of trusting attachment and upbringing in childhood. In their opinion, a healthy emotional connection with parents and educators for a child is the basis of mental stability. Uzbek psychologist G'. Haydarov (2020) associates the problems with children's behavior in preschool institutions with incorrect upbringing methods.

The negative consequences of punitive upbringing methods are widely covered in the literature. Research conducted by T. Kadirova (2021) has shown that a lack of affection in the upbringing process leads to aggression, tearfulness, instability, and mental stress in children.

Also, the information and recommendations "On the Rights of the Child" published by the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan state that violence or negative attitude towards children poses a threat to mental health.

The literature also indicates the need for regular provision of psychological knowledge to parents as a prevention of pedagogical errors. Therefore, improving the psychological literacy of each teacher and parent should be one of the main tools in the modern educational system. The research part was conducted among primary school students of 3 preschool educational institutions and 2 secondary schools in the region. A total of 50 children, 30 parents and 10 educators were studied through interviews and observations. Through questions, an attempt was made to determine the child's mental state, level of self-esteem, and ability to freely express their opinions.

According to the results, 60% of children experienced self-doubt, fear, and intimidation from their parents. It was found that 40% of children were constantly criticized and compared, and it was difficult for them to freely express their opinions. In interviews with educators, many parents confirmed a negative approach to the child, punishment, and neglect.

It was also observed that negative changes in the child's psyche negatively affect his or her ability to engage in social communication. This situation was manifested in children through symptoms such as psychological difficulties, behavioral problems, crying and moodiness. Based on the results of the study, practical recommendations were developed for educators and parents. In particular, psychological seminars were held on recognizing the child's feelings, treating them with kindness, and taking into account the child's mental state in upbringing.

Discussion and results

The results of the study revealed the serious negative impact of incorrect approaches to upbringing on the psyche of children. Based on observations and interviews, it was found that frequent problems in the upbringing process - constant scolding, neglect, excessive punishment, comparing the child with others, ignoring their opinions - cause negative changes in the psychological development of children. In particular, this situation reduces the child's self-confidence, weakens his ability to express himself, and increases internal instability. Observations conducted in preschool and primary schools in the Andijan region showed that imbalances in the psychological state are very widespread among children. Some of them were observed to be excessively shy, while others were aggressive or discontented.

This complicates the child's communication with peers, his attitude to study, and even his acceptance of his own personality. In order for a child to establish healthy psychological relationships with those around him, first of all, there must be warmth, affection, understanding and spiritual support in the family environment. The positive and negative aspects of upbringing form a child's spiritual portrait. A psychologically stable, freely expressing his opinion, active and socially adapted child is the product of a healthy upbringing environment. On the contrary, a child who grows up under constant scolding, punishment, and neglect is prone to social isolation, loneliness, internal dissatisfaction and instability. During the interviews, although parents often considered the external environment or "stubborn character" to be the cause of negative behavior in their children, it was proven that in fact most of these cases are the result of incorrect upbringing methods. It was also found that regular work of school psychologists with children and parents helps to strengthen mental health.

Conclusion

The results of the study show that any educational mistake made in childhood leaves a deep mark on the child's psyche. In particular, constant criticism, punishment, comparison or neglect of a child undermines his mental health. In such an environment, a child may feel insignificant, unnecessary or a "bad child". Incorrect upbringing methods reduce the child's level of social adaptation, weaken his ability to communicate, and he may become a person who cannot express his opinion openly and lives with internal dissatisfaction. This can become the root of not only family but also social problems. In conclusion, in the process of upbringing, parents and educators need to deeply feel what kind of psychological imprint each of their words and actions leaves on the child. They should serve the formation of a mentally healthy person by understanding the child's psychological needs, showing him love, and valuing his opinion. Based on this article, it is recommended that preschools and schools should organize psychological trainings, lectures, and discussions for parents and educators. Because a mentally healthy child is the foundation of a mentally healthy society.

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